

Influence Of Attractiveness Of The Celebrity On Consumer Purchase Intention Of Public University Students

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Abstract

The study focused on the influence of attractiveness of the celebrity on consumer purchase intention of public university students. All the 57,715 students of the public universities in Western Kenya were targeted, they include: Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology with a student population of 25,000, Kibabii University with a student population of 11,715, and lastly Maseno University with a population size of 21,000. The study used the sample of 397 students of the three picked public Universities in Western Kenya, purposive sampling was utilized to sample three Ariel merchandisers promoting Ariel detergent in the three major towns in Western Kenya where the universities are located (Kakamega county, Bungoma county and Kisumu county). Data was then gathered through structured questionnaires and interview schedules. The investigation uncovered that attractiveness of the Celebrity has a statistically significant influence on the Consumer Purchase Intention of Public University Students Western, Kenya as per the study. The study concluded that the celebrity endorsement factor- attractiveness of the celebrity had significantly strong positive causal influence on the customer purchase intentions. The study recommends that brands and marketers to have proper consideration of celebrity attributes while selecting celebrity endorsers. Marketers should consider other salient factors involved when using celebrity endorsement as a promotion tool.

Keywords: Celebrity Attractiveness, Consumer Purchase Intention, Public University Students, Celebrity Endorsement, Western Kenya

INTRODUCTION

There has been big tendency of big and world known brands like Gucci, Nike, Adidas, Chanel, setting aside quite a big sum of their budget for such endorsement contracts. In Kenya, various celebrities have been involved to market various products and it is increasingly becoming a leading strategy among various marketers in the country. Celina is endorsing Harpic toilet cleaner, Terry Anne Chebet endorsing Molfix diapers, Jeff Koinange and Yvonne Okwara Matole endorsing Standard Chartered Bank. The international alcohol brand Glenfiddich unveiled their new bottle in Kenya in the June 2020 which they christened 'the refresh' endorsed by Kenyan reknown chef Mulunda Kombo. These are all products with different levels of involvement for the customer, they are different product lines and are all using the fame and popularity of these celebrities to gain competitive advantage. Despite the advertisement of products by celebrities, firms and companies still opt for more diverse approaches of advertisements, an indication that endorsement of products by celebrities in Kenya might still not be as effective. In the face of social media, and a world where consumers are very vocal about their brand preferences, it is important for brands

and marketers to be strategic with their advertisements. University students particularly have been shown to influence each other and accompany each other to purchase goods (Zhao, Yhang, Liu, Yhang, Bao and Ren, 2020). They form a big population of the market, are young adults who are getting into the independence phase. Being able to understand such a huge market segment and influence their purchasing intentions would be an advantage to any company. Procter & Gamble East Africa (PGEA) in Kenya has been using celebrities such as Mercy Masika (the famous gospel singer in Kenya) to promote Ariel detergent. The advert tends to portray Ariel detergent as the best among other powder detergents in removing stains in one wash (Nzomo, 2013).

However, PGEA still resolved to adopting other advertisement approaches such as "One wash" detergent advertising campaign. In a world of cut throat brand competition, scramble for market share, all the while looking at the bottom line, there is need for more insight. This means more insight on categories of consumers that are influenced by celebrity endorsement, selection of celebrity endorsers, and understanding on

which particular traits of such celebrity endorsers have more strength. The study therefore sought to examine celebrity endorsement factors that if enhanced, would in return enhance consumer purchase intentions of a given product. As far as this research is concerned, there are few if any, documented studies which assessed celebrity endorsement efficiency attributes as well as consumer purchasing intentions in Western Kenya. As such, this study assessed efficacy of dimensions of celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase intentions among public university students in Western Kenya, focusing on Ariel detergent as object of study.

Significance of the Study

This study gives insight on aspects of celebrities that consumers are more likely to be influenced by. It will also give guidelines to Kenyan brands and marketers for when celebrity endorsement is most effective while targeting consumer purchase intentions as well as give insight on the celebrity characters to be considered in building perceived brand personality. The perspectives and findings surfeit of the proposed study will certainly provide a preface for more comprehensive future research. The findings will enrich the theories of source attractiveness, source credibility, and dual entertainment theory for academicians especially those interested in studying the Kenyan consumer markets.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Empirical Review

Attractiveness of the Celebrity and Consumer Purchase Intention

The physical beauty including sportsmanship, charm, grace and intelligence are essential determinants of the purchase decision (Nelson, 2010). Physical beauty is defined by Hakimi, Abedniya, and Zaeim (2011) as features that are widespread, unavoidable, subtle, and surpass cultural boundaries in their impact. Samat et al. (2016) said that attractiveness is about the celebrities traits which are likeable to the consumers.

According to Jamil and Hassan (2014), beauty enhances social acceptability and catches coverage of the media. Pughazhendi and Ravhindran (2012) says that consumers have celebrities they follow and in a case where such celebrities are engaged to endorse a product such consumers will be easily drawn into accepting the message of their celebrity endorser especially in cases where the celebrity message mirrors an aspect of their lives that is touchy and particular with a memory they treasure. Dzisah and Ocloo (2013) said that humans also acquire knowledge about items through imitation and copying. Beautiful and handsome celebrities easily influence customers' beliefs and attitudes (Anosh and Hamad, 2015).

Kahle and Homer (1985) study demonstrated that advertisers shape a stereotype about products; celebrity physical appearance may influence the buyers to the product positively. However, Baker and Churchill (1977) found that physical attractiveness can be handy for product evaluation but not for purchase intentions. Mobile phone advertisement has considered use of famous faces over strange ones. Sometimes the foreign endorser takes over the advertisement and thereby negatives the effort of the producer in marketing the brand (Pandey, 2011). Additionally, a study by Hakimi, Abedniya & Zaeim (2011) on physical attractiveness showed that brand ambassadors attractiveness produces a positive influence to the sales. The study also found that attractiveness is relative to the consumers and many vary from person to person. Producers should consider this in designing their marketing strategies for effective results. In a Malaysian study by Jain (2011) on the influence of physical attractiveness of endorsers on likeability of a brand in commercial banks revealed a positive correlation between endorsers' attractive attributes and likeability of a brand. Further, Yusoff and Khan (2013) in a study in Indonesian hotels found that an attractive endorser influences consumer attitudes towards a brand.

Knowledge Gap

Previous studies on celebrity endorsement and consumer purchase intention have largely been conducted in developed economies or urban commercial contexts, with limited focus on public university students in Kenya—particularly in Western Kenya. There exists a gap in understanding how celebrity attractiveness, as a component of endorsement, influences consumer purchase intention among this demographic group.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This investigation utilized descriptive research design because it plans to collect quantitative data that would explain the traits of celebrity endorsement and purchase intention among Kenyan consumers. The descriptive survey was picked since it is ideal in collecting data in social research that is concerned with the description of the state of the variables and detailed description of phenomena that has already occurred (Punch and Oncaea, 2014; Mertler, 2019). Sabana (2014) states that this strategy is recommendable because the approach researchers to gather quantitative data that can be analyzed quantitatively using inferential analysis.

Target Population

This is units sets, entirely, for which research data are to be utilized for conclusions; it identifies the units for which study discoveries are expected to generalize (Mertler, 2019). This study targeted population is

57,715 students of the public universities and University colleges in Western Kenya, this include: Maseno University, Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, as well as Kibabii University. To determine the target population size, the study adopted the student population from the various university websites.

Table 1: Study Population

University/ College	Population	% Population
Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology.	25,000	43%
Kibabii University	11,715	20%
Maseno University	21,000	37%
Total	57,715	100%

Source: Respective University Websites for 2020

The study involved three Ariel product merchandisers from each of three towns (Kakamega town, Bungoma town and Maseno town, where the respective universities are located), as key informants to provide key information on the celebrity endorsement and Ariel product consumer purchase intentions.

Sample Size

This research utilized the following formula to establish the study sample size:

Equation 1: Formula for Determination of Sample Size (Yamane, 1967);

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n = the sample size

N = the population size

e^2 = desired level of statistical significance (0.05)

Therefore;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} = \frac{57,715}{1 + 57,715(0.05)^2} = 397.2468 \approx 397$$

Thus, the study adopted a sample of 397 respondents that was a representative of the consumer residents of the three universities in Western Kenya.

To determine the sample size of each i^{th} town, the study used proportionate stratified random sampling. A proportion of the sample size was calculated to establish the respondents in each stratum (i^{th} town) to be examined as follows:

$$Proportion = \frac{Samplen}{PopulationN} = \frac{397}{57,715} = 0.00687862773975569$$

Therefore, the i^{th} town sample size was as calculated in table 3.2 below:

Table 2: Study Population and Sample Sizes

City/Town	Population Size	Proportion	Sample size
MMUST	25,000	0.00687862773975569	172
Kibabii University	11,715	0.00687862773975569	81
Maseno University	21,000	0.00687862773975569	144
Total	57,715		397

Source: Respective University Websites

Data Collection Instruments

Well-designed structured questionnaires was employed to get information from the study respondents who are part of the student population in three selected public Universities in Western Kenya (Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, Maseno University and Kibabii University). Interview schedule was employed to gather information from key informants, who are the Ariel product merchandisers in the major towns where the Universities are located; Kakamega town, Bungoma town and Luanda town). This was through purposive sampling to ensure the merchandiser’s were serving a huge student population in the area, and are indeed merchandisers of the Ariel detergent.

Data Collection

With the help of six research assistants, the researcher disseminated the research instrument. A period of one week was given to the respondents in collecting data by filling out questionnaires. The study adopted this approach since the approach minimized on the costs and time involved during fieldwork. The questionnaire approach of data collection enabled the researcher to gather adequate information that is not biased; thus, answers were in respondents’ own thinking. The questionnaire method of data collecting also provided enough time for research participants to provide thoughtful responses.

Ethical Considerations

In this study ethics was considered accordingly as by Breweton *et al.* (2001) as follows: The researcher sought the consent and attention of interviewee (key informants for the study) before conducting any interview and explain to them the aim of the interview and the privacy expected of the data to be given. There was appropriate acknowledgement of any other scholars’ research work and materials used through proper citation of the sources of the reference.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Response Rate

The researcher delivered 397 questionnaires at random to study participants who are students at three different public universities in Western Kenya (Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, Kibabii University, and Maseno University). Fortunately, 370

of 397 questionnaires were duly filled and given back. This results in a response rate of 93 percent (see table 4.1), which coincides with Zikmund's (2010) argument that a response rate of more than 50.0 percent is required for generalization of the findings' conclusions.

Table 3: Response Rate

City/Town	Sample size	Participants	Return Rate (%)
MMUST	172	120	94%
Kibabii University	81	60	87%
Maseno University	144	190	95%
Total	397	370	93%

For the interviews, the study selected one Ariel merchant from each of the three regions of the selected Universities (Kakamega town near MMUST, Bungoma town near Kibabii University, and Luanda town near Maseno University). All the three merchants accepted and were accessible for the interview to provide key information on the Ariel detergent celebrity endorsement and its influence on the consumer purchase intentions.

Demographic Characteristics

Respondent demographic information comprised the respondent's university, gender, age, and greatest educational level obtained. The results were as predicted in figure 1.

Figure 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

According to the figure, 65 percent of the respondents were male, while 35 percent were female; this indicates that the study guaranteed gender parity throughout the data gathering procedure.

It is also apparent that the bulk of respondents (44 percent) were between the ages of 26 and 35, as seen in figure 1. While 28 % were between the ages of 36 and 45, 17 percent were under the age of 25, and 11 % were

46 and above, indicating that the most of respondents were mature enough to provide trustworthy information for this study. Furthermore, 59 % had a University first degree and % had reached the Diploma level of education, indicating that the most of respondents were suitably literate enough to grasp the researcher's questions posed in the field. As a result, the information provided may be depended on for this study.

Descriptive Statistics

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the descriptive statistics of the study's dependent variable (consumer purchase intentions) as well as the independent factors (attractiveness of celebrity).

Consumer Purchase Intention of Public University Students.

The purpose of the study was to the descriptive statistics of Ariel detergent purchase intention amongst public university students in Western Kenya in order to determine the level of Ariel detergent purchase intentions among the students. Table 4 shows the findings.

Table 4: Descriptive Analysis for Consumer Purchase Intention. Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1, Disagree (D) = 2, Undecided (U) = 3, Agree (A) = 4, Strongly Agree (SA) = 5.

Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
I have interest to find information about the Ariel-detergent.	27	19	135	142	47
	7%	5%	36%	38%	13%
I'm considering to purchase the Ariel detergent	16	22	69	177	86
	4%	6%	19%	48%	23%
I'm interested to try the Ariel detergent	19	84	64	142	61
	5%	23%	17%	38%	16%
I want to know further information about the Ariel detergent	13	89	112	86	70
	4%	24%	30%	23%	19%
I want to have the P&G's Ariel detergent.	37	72	64	133	64
	10%	19%	17%	36%	17%
I will convince my friends to use the Ariel detergent	23	44	136	102	65
	6%	12%	37%	28%	18%

Average level of CPI	Mean (%Mean)	Std. Dev.	Std. Error of mean	Minimum	Maximum
	3.436 (69%)	.70751	.03678	1.17	5.00

The findings uncovers that a bulk of the respondents, 38% that they are having interest to find information about the Ariel-detergent, but 36% are undecided; this is an indication that not everyone is having interest in the Ariel detergent product. The sample findings also shows that 48% agreed that they are considering to purchase the Ariel detergent, 38% agreed that they are

interested in trying the Ariel detergent. Similarly, 30% and 23% were undecided and agreed respectively that they want to know further information about the Ariel detergent. Similarly, most of the respondents, concurred that they want to have P&G's Ariel detergent. In terms of convincing others to buy the Ariel detergent product, majority of the respondents, 37% were undecided if they would be able to convince their friends to use the Ariel detergent. On average, the study uncovered that the overall level of customer purchase intentions among the selected University students in Western Kenya was found to be 69% (mean = 3.436, Std. Dev. = 0.70751) rated moderate; an exhibition that the intentions of buying sAriel product among the selected University Students in Western Kenya are not high thus need for enhancement. The study therefore sought to assess if endorsement of the Ariel detergent product by celebrities would enhance intentions of the public university students in Western Kenya to purchase the product.

Attractiveness of Celebrity.

The research intended to assess the descriptive statistics of celebrity attractiveness and its influence on the purchase intention among public university students in Western Kenya. This would assist in determining the level of satisfaction among the public university students in Western Kenya and how it would influence the Ariel detergent intentions to purchase. Table 4.12 exhibits the findings.

Table 5: Descriptive Analysis for Attractiveness of the Celebrity. Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1, Disagree (D) = 2, Undecided (U) = 3, Agree (A) = 4, Strongly Agree (SA) = 5.

Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
The advertisement with the celebrity gets my attention more than the advertisement without the celebrity endorser.	17 5%	15 4%	113 31%	52 14%	173 47%
The advertisement with celebrity is more favorable to remember than advertisement without the celebrity endorser.	12 3%	29 8%	115 31%	167 45%	47 13%
The advertisement with celebrity is more beautiful than advertisement without the celebrity endorser.	6 2%	173 47%	54 15%	65 18%	72 19%
The advertisement with celebrity is more popular than advertisements without the celebrity endorser.	25 7%	62 17%	37 10%	181 49%	64 17%
The advertisement with celebrity is classier and sexier than advertisement without the celebrity endorser.	56 15%	111 30%	41 11%	78 21%	84 23%
I believe that products that are advertised by celebrities are of good quality.	63 17%	118 32%	54 15%	58 16%	77 21%
Average Level of Attractiveness of the Celebrity	Mean(%Mea n) 3.2450 (65%)	Std. Dev. 0.7822 2	Std. Error of mean 0.0406 7	Minimum 1.83	Maximum 5.00

Clearly, majority of the respondents strongly agreed that the advertisement with the celebrity gets their attention more than the advertisement without the celebrity endorser as indicated by 47% in table 4.12. Similarly, 45% of the respondents thought that the advertisement with celebrity is more favorable to remember than advertisement without the celebrity endorser. On the contrary, 47%, 49% agreed that advertisement with celebrity is more popular than advertisements without the celebrity endorser. In contrast, 30% and 32% of the respondents respectively disagreed that the advertisement with celebrity is more beautiful than advertisement without the celebrity endorser, and that the advertisement with celebrity is classier and sexier than advertisement without the celebrity endorser and disagreed that they believe that goods advertised by celebrities are of good quality respectively. Overall, the average level of attractiveness of the Celebrity was at 65% (mean= 3.2450, Std. dev. = 0.78222) rated moderate. The study therefore purposed to assess the influence of celebrity attractiveness on the purchase intention among public university students in Western Kenya.

Correlation Analysis

The study utilized correlation analysis, in specific Pearson moment correlation (r) to evaluate the strength as well as direction of the relationship among celebrity endorsement i.e. Attractiveness of the Celebrity and Consumer Purchase Intention among public university students in Western,

Table 6: Correlation Matrix

	Consumer Purchase Intentions	Gender of Celebrity	Credibility of the Celebrity	Attractiveness of Celebrity	Multiple Celebrity Endorsement
Consumer Purchase Intentions	1				
Gender of Celebrity	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	370			
Attractiveness of Celebrity	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.674**	.330**	.696**	1
Multiple Celebrity Endorsement	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.000	.000	.000	370
** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					

The table shows that there was strong positive correlation between Consumer Purchase intentions as well as celebrity endorsement variables (attractiveness of the Celebrity) among public university students in Western, Kenya as indicated by $r = 0.674$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$.

Simple Linear Regression between Attractiveness of Celebrity and Consumer Purchase Intentions

The study's third objective of the study was to determine the effect of attractiveness of the celebrity on consumer purchase intention of public university students in Western Kenya.

Attractiveness of the celebrity has no significant influence on the consumer purchase intention of public university students.

Table 7: Linear Regression Analysis for the Attractiveness of Celebrity and Consumer Purchase Intentions

Model Summary					
Model	r	r-square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.674 ^a	.455	.453	.52318	
a. Predictors: (Constant), Attractiveness of the Celebrity					
b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Purchase Intentions					
ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
1 Regression	83.979	1	83.979	306.803	.000 ^b
Residual	100.730	368	.274		
Total	184.708	369			
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Purchase Intentions					
b. Predictors: (Constant), Attractiveness of Celebrity					
Coefficients ^a					
Model		Standardized Coefficients		t	p-value
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error		
1	(Constant)	1.457	.116	12.537	.000
	Attractiveness of Celebrity	.610	.035	.674	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Purchase Intentions					

ANOVA test findings were $F(1, 368) = 306.803$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$, indicating that the Simple Linear Regression model suited our dataset well. The model (Attractiveness of the Celebrity) managed to clarify 45.5% of the variation in consumer purchase intention of Public University Students Western, Kenya as indicated by the $r\text{-square} = 0.263$ as shown in table 7's model summary. The unstandardized beta coefficient was significant, $\beta = 0.610$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$ as shown by the regression coefficient results; therefore, the study did not accept the null hypothesis and resolved that Attractiveness of the Celebrity has a statistically significant influence on the Consumer Purchase Intention of Public University Students Western, Kenya. Attractiveness of the Celebrity had a positive standardized beta coefficient = 0.674 as exhibited in table 7's the coefficients results exhibiting that a unit improvement in the Attractiveness of the Celebrity was likely to cause an improvement in the Consumer Purchase Intentions of University Students in Western Kenya by 67.4%. To predict the Consumer Purchase Intention of Public University Students Western, Kenya when given the Attractiveness of the Celebrity level, the following model is suggested by the study; $\text{Consumer Purchase Intentions} = 1.457 + 0.610 \text{ Attractiveness of the Celebrity}$

The empirical findings were supported by key informants who agreed that attractiveness of the celebrity had a significant influence on the Ariel detergent consumer purchase intentions as indicated by 100% response in support as shown in figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Attractiveness of celebrity and its influence on customer purchase intentions

The explanation given by the key informants suggested that sales of Ariel detergent in the market also depends on the attractiveness of the celebrity used to advertise the product on the market as indicated in the quote below:

.... attractiveness of the celebrity in advertising any product is one of the key traits that a customer will look at before buying the product. Appearance of a celebrity in an advert always boosts the confidence in the customer that the product is reliable. Imagine someone advertising Ariel detergent but walking in dirty white clothes, how will that sound to the customer.

However, the according to key the informant, the celebrity should also look attractive in the advert in so as to draw more customers to purchase the commodity as indicated in the quote below:

.... celebrities involved in any advert should make sure that they physically look attractive to the target customers. Imagine someone advertising Ariel detergent in dirty white clothes, how will that sound to the customer...

The findings of our study complement with the findings of a study by Jamil and Hassan (2014) who asserted that attractiveness enhances social reception as well as catches media coverage. Also, Pughazhendi and Ravhindran (2012) says that consumers have celebrities they follow and in a case where such celebrities are engaged to endorse a product such consumers will be easily drawn into accepting the message of their

celebrity endorser especially in cases where the celebrity message mirrors an aspect of their lives that is touchy and particular with a memory they treasure. Dzisah and Ocloo (2013) said that humans also acquire knowledge about items through imitation and copying. Beautiful and handsome celebrities easily influence customers' beliefs and attitudes (Anosh and Hamad, 2015).

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The study findings regarding attractiveness of the celebrity revealed that customers are attracted to a particular commodity based on the popularity of the celebrity advertising it. That advertisement with celebrity is more beautiful, classier and sexier than advertisement without the celebrity endorsers. The majority of customers feel that products advertised by popular celebrities are of high quality, which leads them to purchase the products. However, the findings revealed that attractiveness of the celebrity endorsing a given product was not certain in persuading customers to buy the product

Conclusion

The study concludes that celebrity gender possess a significant influence on customer purchase intentions. That for products associated with women, due to the societal gender roles, for example the Ariel detergent, consumers would be persuaded to buy the commodity if it is advertised, promoted and endorsed by a female celebrity. The study also concluded that the celebrity's attractiveness has a statistically significant strong positive influence on the customer purchase intentions. That advertisement with popular celebrities who are considered more beautiful and classier influenced more, enjoyed more brand recall compared to advertisements without endorsement from popular celebrities with such attributes.

Recommendations

Since attractiveness of a celebrity was uncovered to have a significant impact on the customer purchase intentions, marketers and companies should consider engaging celebrities that are popular and considered attractive to endorse their products since such advertisements are likely to get more attention and influence consumers more than advertisements without celebrity endorsers thus persuading customers to buy the products. Brands that wish to use celebrities to market their products should consider using the approach of multiple endorsers since it is indeed convincing, dynamic and thus influencing more customers to buy the advertised product.

Contribution of the Study

This study contributes to filling this gap by examining the relationship between the attractiveness of celebrities and the purchasing behavior of public university students in Western Kenya. The findings will help establish context-specific insights applicable to Kenyan markets and extend the empirical scope of celebrity endorsement theories within developing-country settings. Celebrities have an important role in promoting products on the markets. Marketers plus companies who would wish to have celebrities promoting their products should consider several factors before engaging them. They should assess how the society perceives the product and whether there are still if any gender roles and biases they associate with the product so that they can engage a celebrity who is best suited considering the factors. The behaviour, trust and reliability of a celebrity to the target customers is also another aspect that marketers and companies should check into before engaging a celebrity to endorse their product. Companies should also consider using more than one celebrity to endorse their product for the approach is likely to lead to enhanced customer purchase intentions.

Suggestions for Further Studies

The investigation revealed that besides the four celebrity endorsement elements (gender of celebrity, credibility and attractiveness of the celebrity, as well as multiple celebrity endorsement), there were other aspects not covered, that would significantly impact intentions of customers in purchasing given product. Future studies should therefore consider exploring these other factors not covered in this study that significantly influence customer purchase intentions. Future studies should also consider carrying out such a comprehensive study across many items, which may be more beneficial to this field of research.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahmed, R.R., Seedani, S.K., Ahuja, M.K., & Paryani, S.K. (2015). Impact of celebrity endorsement on consumer buying behavior. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 16, 12-22.
- [2] Akinyi, R.J. (2017). *The influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer's purchasing decisions of fast-moving consumer goods among low and middle social class in Nairobi County, Kenya*. (Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya).
- [3] Anosh, M., & Hamad, N. (2015). Client sensitivity about celebrity endorsement: A study of FMCG trademarks. *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 4(3), 1-4.

- [4] Apeyoje, A. (2013). Influence of celebrity endorsement of advertisement on students' purchase intention. *Mass Communication and Journalism*, 3(3), 1-7.
- [5] Baker, M. J., & Churchill Jr, G. A. (1977). The impact of physically attractive models on advertising evaluations. *Journal of Marketing research*, 14(4), 538-555.
- [6] Breweton, P. & Millward, L. 2001. *Organizational Research Methods*, London, SAGE.
- [7] Bryman, A. & Bell, E. 2003. *Business research methods*, Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- [8] Du Plessis, P.J. & Rousseau, G.G. (2007). *Buyer Behaviour: Understanding Consumer Psychology and Marketing*. Cape Town: Oxford University Press.
- [9] Dzisah, W.E., & Ocloo, C.E. (2013). Celebrity endorsement and consumer buying behaviour; enhancing the promotion function of marketing in the central business area of Accra, Ghana. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(25), 197-208.
- [10] Friedman, H & Friedman, L. (1979). Endorser effectiveness by product type. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 19(5), 63-71.
- [11]. Hakimi, P.N., Abedniya, B., & Zaeim, T.B. (2011). Lessons from the rich and famous: a cross-cultural comparison of celebrity endorsement in advertising, *Journal of Advertising*, 34(2), 85-98.
- [12] Hussain, R., & Ali, M. (2015). Effect of store atmosphere on consumer purchase intention. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 7(2). 206.
- [13] Jain, A., & Patel, R. (nd). Effectiveness of Celebrity Endorsers in Various Product Categories. *Journal of Marketing Trends*, 1(2).
- [14] Jain, V. (2011). Celebrity Endorsement and Its Impact on Sales: A research Analysis Carried Out in India, *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 11(4), 67-84.
- [15] Jamil, R.A. & Hassan, S.R. (2014). Influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase intention for existing products: A comparative study. *Journal of Management Info*, 4(1), 1-23.
- [16] Kahle, L. R., & Homer, P. M. (1985). Physical attractiveness of the celebrity endorser: A social adaptation perspective. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 11(4), 954-961.
- [17] Khan, S. K. Rukhsar, A. Shoaib, M. (2016). Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on Consumer Purchase Intention. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 18(1), 6-9.
- [18] Mertler. C. A. (2019). *Introduction to Educational Research*. 2nd Ed. Sage publications. New Delhi
- [19] Nzomo V. (2013). Unilever [Omo] vs Procter & Gamble [Ariel]: Regulation of Advertising under Kenya's Competition and Intellectual Property Laws. <https://cipit.strathmore.edu/unilever-omo-vs-procter-gamble-ariel-regulation-of-advertising-under-kenyas-competition-and-intellectual-property-laws/>
- [20] Pandey, V. K. (2011). Impact of celebrity endorsement on young Generation through TV Advertisement. *VSRD International Journal of Business & Management Research*, 1(10), 226-231.
- [21] Pughazhendi, A. & Ravindran, D.S. (2012). A study on the influence of using celebrity endorsements on consumer buying behaviour in Tamil Nadu, India. *Journal of Research in International Business Management*, 2(4), 89-96.
- [22] Punch, K.F., & Oancea, A. (2014). *Introduction to Research Methods in Education*. 2nd Ed. Sage Publications. New Delhi.
- [23] Sabana, B. M. (2014). Entrepreneur financial literacy, financial access, transaction costs and performance of micro enterprises in Nairobi City County, Kenya. *An unpublished PHD project University of Nairobi, Nairobi, Kenya*.
- [24] Samat, M.F., Abu Bakar, H., & Annual, N. (2016). Endorser credibility and its Influence on The purchase intention of social networking sites consumer: A mediating role of attitudes toward SNS advertising. *International Journal of Management and Applied Science*, 2(12), 50-56.
- [25] Yusoff, R. M., & Khan, F. (2013). Stress and Burnout in the Higher Education Sector in Pakistan: A Systematic Review of Literature. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*, 2(11), 90-98.
- [26] Zhao, R., Yang, M., Liu, J., Yang, L., Bao, Z., & Ren, X. (2020). University Students' Purchase Intention and Willingness to Pay for Carbon-Labeled Food Products: *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 17(19), 7026. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17197026>.